

DELIVERABLE 5.4

DEVELOPMENT AND

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE

EXPLOITATION PLAN

AUTHORS

Annalaura Silvestro

Riccardo Porro

Valentina Amorese

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report is one of the outcomes of the FoodCLIC project, a Horizon Europe funded Innovation Action project that fosters the development of healthy, sustainable and inclusive urban food environments. To achieve this goal, this report aims to propose a first tentative exploitation scheme. The real-life interventions that FoodCLIC seeks to implement and scale will allow city-regions to fill gaps in their knowledge and build an evidence-base for transformative food policy-making and planning. This project builds on the place-based CLIC framework (Sonnino & Milbourne, 2022), which seeks to achieve food system transformation by considering integrated food policy outcomes with regards to: *co-benefits* between economic, social and environmental objectives; *linkages* between urban, peri-urban and rural areas and between the land and the sea; *inclusion* of citizens (including in particular marginalized and vulnerable groups) and other stakeholders in the design, implementation and monitoring of policies; and *connectivity* between the food system and other sectors and policies, such as waste, water and the built environment. This framework puts forward that sustainable food system transformation can be achieved through implementing innovations that can deliver, as far as possible, all four outcomes (Mattioni, Milbourne, & Sonnino, 2022).

Task 5.4 aims to develop an Exploitation Plan (D5.4) for the short, medium and longer terms to make FoodCLIC's results usable for a wide range of stakeholders. This specifically concerns the comprehensive and practical set of principles, guidelines and tools for the development of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks, multi-stakeholder engagement and communities' empowerment, monitoring systems, innovative business models and market conditions (T4.5).

Since exploitation is heavily context-dependent (e.g., the commercial sector will apply FoodCLIC's results differently from academia or local authorities), this plan is propaedeutic to the development of tailor-made investment schemes and innovative inclusive business models shaped around each of the project's result.

1.1 THE REPORT STRUCTURE

The present deliverable is structured in 5 chapters, starting from the clarification of the report's goal (Chapter 1). Chapter 2 describes the role of exploiting project results in a more general way and within the context of sustainable food system and food policies development, Chapter 3 provides an overview of the methodology followed to structure the FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan, and Chapter

4 details the first Key Exploitable Results description. Finally, Chapter 5 wraps up the conclusion of the Deliverable, providing also the view of next steps to be followed in future months to refine and elaborate the final FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan.

1.2 HOW TO USE THIS REPORT

This document is the first step towards the development of a tailor-made Exploitation Plan targeting the results of FoodCLIC's Living Labs (LLs). It aims to support and strengthen the activities of the LLs in the project's eight city-regions – Aarhus (Denmark), Amsterdam (Netherlands), Barcelona (Spain), Berlin (Germany), Brasov (Romania), Budapest (Hungary), Lisbon (Portugal) and Lucca (Italy) by:

- **Supporting the inclusion of exploitation in the core strategic thinking towards the development of Urban Food Policies (UFP);**
- **Identifying key steps in the development of the Exploitation Plan;**
- **Providing recommendations on how to develop an effective Exploitation Plan;**
- **Inspiring both municipalities and the Living Lab teams' actions with a possible model of exploitation scheme.**

Please note that this document is the first early version of the FoodCLIC Exploitation plan. It aims at providing a first overview and initial analysis of the exploitation and sustainability of FoodCLIC implementations. The final version of the plan will be delivered at the end of the project (M54), including updated actions, timings and IPR strategies.

2. THE CONTEXT

Cities have a potential key role in addressing food system challenges where there is a need for integrated policy action at all levels (Hawkes & Halliday, 2017) (D2.1). Indeed, city regions are becoming living laboratories for the development of new solutions fostering food system transformation. Over the past decade Europe has played a key role in that respect, catalyzing changes by supporting transformation towards inclusive future-proof food systems. This field of action is relatively new, but extremely fertile and promising. There is a shared “agreement in the literature that an integrated UFP [Urban Food Policy] framework could push ahead just and sustainable transformations” (D2.1).

2.1 EXPLOITATION PLAN BEST PRACTICES

Several studies have identified best practices for the exploitation of project results in European projects. One such study by (Brouwer, Kok, & Hekkert, 2016) identified several key factors that contribute to successful exploitation of project results, including the development of a clear exploitation plan early in the project, the engagement of stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, and the establishment of partnerships with industry partners to facilitate commercialization. The European Commission's guidelines on the exploitation of project results (2017) also emphasize the importance of identifying potential commercial applications of project results and outline strategies for protecting intellectual property and facilitating commercialization (European Commission, 2017).

Engaging with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle is also identified as a best practice for the successful exploitation of project results (European Commission, 2017). This includes engaging with potential customers and partners to identify commercial opportunities for project results, as well as engaging with end-users to ensure that project results are aligned with their needs. Finally, establishing partnerships with industry partners is critical for enabling the commercialization of project results. Such partnerships can provide access to expertise and resources needed to bring project results to the market, as well as facilitate the development of licensing paths, joint ventures or spin-off companies.

In addition to these best practices, effective communication and dissemination strategies are key aspects to be considered to maximize the impact of project results, as well as the awareness to adapt results to changing market conditions and the availability of funding and resources to support commercialization efforts. European Commission's guidelines also emphasize the importance of **protecting intellectual property**, which is essential for enabling the commercialization of project

results. Beneficiaries are encouraged to develop strategies for protecting intellectual property rights, such as filing for patents or trademarks, and to ensure that intellectual property ownership is clearly defined in project contracts (European Commission, 2017).

Despite the importance of the exploitation of project results, several barriers can hinder their exploitation. These include the lack of commercial potential of project results, the difficulty of securing funding for commercialization activities, and the lack of awareness of potential commercial applications (European Commission, 2017). Overall, the exploitation of project results is a crucial issue for European projects, with significant implications for innovation, society and EU economic growth. Overall, and in line with the paragraphs above, in order to ensure the development of successful exploitation plan, it is important to:

- **start developing valid models of exploitation plans from the very beginning of the project;**
- **engage with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle;**
- **establish partnerships with industry partners;**
- **foster the participation of funding agencies as they can provide funding for commercialization activities and promote the development of partnerships between academic researchers and industry partners.**

2.2 THE IMPACT OF PROJECT RESULTS EXPLOITATION TO SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

Sustainable food systems are characterized by their ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, and they require innovation and collaboration across sectors and disciplines (FAO, 2018). In this context, European projects that focus on sustainable food systems can generate knowledge and technologies that can be exploited to support the development of more sustainable food policies and practices.

The exploitation of project results from European projects might have a range of impacts on the development of sustainable food systems and the support of food policies. For example, the development of new technologies or practices can support the adoption of more sustainable production methods, such as reducing the use of pesticides or improving water management (European Commission, 2016). Exploiting project results can also support the development of more sustainable supply chains, through the development of new logistics systems or improved traceability and labeling.

In addition to these direct impacts, the exploitation of project results can support the development of more effective and inclusive Food Policies by endorsing policy frameworks and guidelines that promote sustainable food production and consumption, or providing evidence for the development of incentive schemes that encourage the adoption of more sustainable practices (European Commission, 2016).

Overall, through the generation of new knowledge, practices and technologies and fostering the collaboration and innovation across sectors and disciplines, European projects have the potential to play a key role in addressing the challenges facing the food system and in promoting more sustainable and equitable food systems.

2.3 INTRODUCING EXPLOITATION PATHS

An Exploitation Plan is an important component of any European project. This is especially true when it involves research and innovation. It outlines the measures and strategies that will be implemented to ensure the successful exploitation of the project results, to maximize their potential impact on the market and society (European Commission, 2023). Overall, it can be argued that the Exploitation Plan is crucial to ensure that the results of a European project are effectively translated into marketable products, services or best practices that benefit society and contribute to economic growth and a sustainable future.

In order to exploit FoodCLIC project results, the Consortium defined different *exploitation paths* that can be followed depending on the nature of the results and the goals of the project:

- ***commercial exploitation*, which aims at creating an economic value from the solution by identifying a market that is willing to pay for it. This can be done for example by developing an innovative platform for food redistribution, which can benefit different stakeholders such as final users, developers, sellers and policy makers;**
- ***Non-commercial exploitation*, which focuses on providing value through the knowledge generated by the solution. This can be achieved, for example, by making a framework or dataset available on an open platform, which can benefit public actors, institutions, researchers and policy makers;**
- ***impact exploitation*, which aims at valorizing the impact generated by the result and encouraging innovation. This can be done, for example, by creating an innovative hub for social inclusion, which can benefit local communities, civil society, organizations and policy makers.**

3. METHODOLOGY

To lay the foundation for the FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan, as well as to ensure sustainability of project results after the end of M54, the Consortium started by performing a background analysis followed by a context analysis of the real-life interventions that FoodCLIC seeks to implement. Based upon the context analysis and literature review, we developed a first draft of the FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan that we discussed with Work Package (WP) and Task Leaders and LL representatives.

As already mentioned, considering that FoodCLIC interventions are currently under development and will be implemented/improved in the next years of activity, FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan will be developed throughout the entire project and will take into consideration also specific Intellectual Property Right (IPR) issues and detailed single exploitation plans. Inputs from FoodCLIC partners will be collected during all the project's life through continuous updates collected during project meetings and collaborative instruments shared with all project partners.

3.1 THE REVIEW PROCESS

To develop this first version of the Exploitation Plan a background analysis was conducted to identify the key themes and nodes of Exploitation Plans of similar European projects. Specifically, more than 13 Exploitation Plans developed within 10 European Projects were analyzed to understand the best practices in the field and to guide the development of our model. Subsequently, a scheme to structure the main parts of the Exploitation Plan development process was defined and discussed with the project coordinators and the WP5 Task Leaders. Based on their suggestions, the model was integrated and improved.

After reflecting on the possible project results, it was necessary to collect initial insights from FoodCLIC WP and Task Leaders. This phase was fundamental to drafting the Exploitation Plan and ensuring its coherence with the project objectives. The interviews were conducted during M7 and M8 by the team using the Microsoft Teams platform and lasted approximately one hour each. Prior to the interviews, a standardized template was shared with the participants, to provide an overview of the information to be collected through the meeting: details on the expected results within the ongoing Tasks; challenges addressed by the result; expected beneficiaries; stakeholders involved; expected benefits; possible exploitation path; and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) associated with the outcome. During the interviews, the WP and Task Leaders shared their insights on expected outcomes and potential exploitation opportunities. Subsequently, the collected data were

processed, analyzed and synthesized to produce a complete and coherent overview to develop the first version of the Exploitation Plan.

Table 1: interviews with FoodCLIC WP and Task Leaders

FoodCLIC PARTNER	INTERVIEWEE	WP	WHEN
ICLEI ES	Anna Bruen, Dorina Meyer, Monika Rut	WP5	March, 16 th 2023
VU and Cascaisambiente	VU: Jacqueline Broerse, Eveliëne Hoop, Leon Feenstra Cascaisambiente: Nadine Rodriguez, Joao Dinis	WP1	March, 22 nd 2023
CU	Ferne Edwards	WP2	March, 27 th 2023
Voedsel Verbindt	Carlo Verhart, Ruben Smolders		
HUB	Julia Behringer	WP3	April, 5 th 2023
VU	Tobia Jones		April, 18 th 2023

3.2 RELATION WITH OTHER WORK PACKAGES

The FoodCLIC exploitation plan is closely tied to the expected outcomes deriving from all projects. Indeed, the Key Exploitable Results described in Chapter 4 are based on the elaboration and analysis of different expected activities and outcomes anticipated from all the work packages, considering their possible exploitation through a commercial, non-commercial and impact path. Table 2 sums up the main expected results deriving from all FoodCLIC WP.

Table 2: WP main expected results

WP	MONTHS	EXPECTED RESULTS
WP1	M1-M48	<p>Definition of methodological guidance to FoodCLIC's activities in WP2-5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ development of training material for LLs, ○ development of the Food Sustainability Tool and the Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation (RMDE) Framework.
WP2	M1-M13	<p>Elaboration of mapping and gapping materials focused on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ good practices for the development and implementation of integrated urban food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks, ○ FPNs' effectiveness in the transition to healthy, circular and resilient urban food systems, ○ food environments, their actors and the identification of existing food deprived and vulnerable groups, ○ city-region specific local policies and actions.
WP3	M3-M48	<p>Co-design and co-implementation of real-life interventions in the different dimensions of the urban food environment by each FPN through their LLs. Since the real-life interventions have not yet been selected, it is not possible to identify concrete results with exploitation potential.</p>
WP4	M2-M54	<p>Supporting knowledge exchange and mutual learning to enhance the transformative capacity of a wide range of food system actors and institutions at the local, national and international levels by establishing close connections between FoodCLIC and other European and global activities; developing a pan-European FPN platform and of an HEI network of research institutions committed to sustainable food systems; analysis, integration and comparison of project results and lessons learned from WP2, WP3 and WP5 (broadening) to translate them into evidence-based recommendations (guidelines and tools) on how to develop real-life interventions in the urban food environments and use them as a leverage point for the formulation of integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks.</p>
WP5	M1-M54	<p>Implementation of communication and dissemination activities related to project findings; management of the Knowledge Hub in respect to all its contents; implementation of a city-to-city learning program with EU and African extension city-regions – to replicate the first phases of the project in that context creating supportive conditions for their city-region food system innovators; implementation of a cities network to allow the share urban food policies good practices from more advanced cities to less experienced ones; establishment of a Think Tank to provide regular feedback on the project's goals, activities, findings, recommendations, and outputs.</p>

3.3 THE EXPLOITATION PLAN MODEL

The main structure of the FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan defined by the Consortium comprises some “building blocks”, which will be included as far as possible in the first Exploitation Plan (this Deliverable) and successively revised and changed during all the project duration:

- **definition of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs): since not all the project results could be interesting and possible to be exploited, it is necessary to identify any valuable project results and the related potential exploitable market;**
- **definition of Beneficiaries and Benefits: it is essential to identify the target group of stakeholders external to the project who have specific needs that can be addressed by the project's knowledge and understand the benefits and impacts provided by project results to each target group. This step helps in understanding whom the project is intended to benefit and how it can meet their needs;**
- **definition of exploitation channels and actions: after identifying the target groups, the next step is to identify channels and actions that can be used to present and spread the project results and involve beneficiaries. This step helps to develop a plan for communicating the project's results to its intended audience, ensuring that the project is well understood and used;**
- **definition of monitoring process: the identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor the project results and exploitation activities will help in evaluating the progress of the project and its effectiveness in meeting its objectives;**
- **finalization of the Exploitation Plan: it is essential to compare expected exploitable results with effective exploited results and identify possible improvements to the first plan drafted during M1-M9. This step helps to evaluate the effectiveness of the exploitation plan and identify ways to improve it.**

The present Delivery presents the first Exploitation Plan, providing a first proposal of which could be the Key Exploitable Results of the FoodCLIC project, the benefits they provide and the beneficiaries addressed. For what concern the definition of specific exploitation channels and actions, the monitoring process and the finalization of the plan, these parts will be included and elaborated in the reviewed and finalized version of the Exploitation Plan (M54).

A key aspect relevant to consider is the existing relation and connection between exploitation activities and communication and dissemination activities. FoodCLIC's communication and dissemination activities will play a critical role in the success of the project by ensuring that their outcomes and results will be effectively shared with relevant stakeholders and end-users. The FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan will involve strategies for bringing research findings and innovations to market, maximizing the societal and economic impact of the project. Therefore, communication and dissemination activities are essential to this process, as they enable project partners to build networks, engage with key stakeholders, and raise awareness about the project's results and potential applications. By running communication and dissemination activities in parallel with the Exploitation Plan, it would be possible to ensure that FoodCLIC outcomes and results will be effectively communicated and disseminated, maximizing their potential impact and contribution to the wider community.

Figure 1: Relation between Exploitation planning and Communication and Dissemination activities

The approach the Consortium has towards the proposal and development of the project Exploitation Plan is coherent with the innovative structure and activities it carries out. Thus, as an Innovation Hub, Cariplo Factory will propose innovative and participatory methodologies for results exploitation valorizing also impact approaches that stand out from what has been developed in other European projects regarding result valorization. Indeed, the Consortium will leverage tools validated and consolidated within Cariplo Factory to actively involve various stakeholders maximizing the impact of FoodCLIC results and promoting innovation and competitiveness in the food sector in an effective and efficient way. In addition to these proposed activities other FoodCLIC partners and city regions involved in the project could also implement other exploitation activities in line with their common

way of working – more standard ones than the ones proposed by the Consortium, such as conferences, focus groups, scientific database and documentation.

Table 3: Possible FoodCLIC results exploitation tools

RESULT EXAMPLE	EXPLOITATION PATH	EXPLOITATION ACTIVITY
Open data/guidelines	Non-commercial	<p><i>Hackathons – collaborative events that bring together programmers, designers, and other experts to develop solutions for specific problems.</i></p> <p>This type of event can be proposed to valorize data gathered and/or guidelines developed in the project.</p>
Innovative business models	Commercial/Impact	<p><i>Investors link and Impact investing tools – financial tools that allow investors to invest their money in companies, organizations, or funds that have a positive social or environmental impact, in addition to generating financial returns. Some examples of impact investing instruments are green bonds, social impact bonds, community development financial institutions, and venture philanthropy.</i></p> <p>This type of instrument can be proposed to allow the scaling up of inclusive and innovative social businesses.</p>
Products	Commercial	<p><i>Match-making Days – events allowing companies to meet and interact with potential innovative businesses or technology partners. The event can be structured through plenary sessions and focused one-to-one or closed group meetings.</i></p> <p><i>Innovation Days – events that bring together innovators, experts, and other stakeholders to discuss new ideas and trends, can be organized by companies or external organizations.</i></p> <p>These types of events can be proposed to present innovative products to companies enabling adoption or further development path.</p>

4. EXPLOITATION PLAN 1.0

The interviews conducted with WP and Task Leaders allowed us to start gathering information about project activities ongoing to derive a possible first overview of future results to be exploited. Since in the first months of project life, it is not already possible to derive what are the key exploitable results among the overall ones produced by the project, and consequently the related exploitation path, monitoring process and future actions – as described by the Exploitation Plan model proposed (Chapter 3).

However, the fine-tuning structure of the Exploitation Plan will allow it to be integrated and evolved during all project life. The first information about possible results to be exploited, deriving from ongoing and closed activities are the following – here reported according to the scheme described in Chapter 3.

4.1 CLASSIFICATION OF PROJECT RESULTS

The FoodCLIC Exploitation Plan provides a comprehensive roadmap for maximizing the impact and sustainability of its results. To deeply analyze project results, they are classified according to their main objective and their category. The present paragraph details the classification before proceeding with the analysis of the results.

OBJECTIVES OF RESULTS

By effectively exploiting project results, European projects can make a significant contribution to food policy definition and food market needs, promoting a more sustainable, healthy and resilient food system for Europe and beyond. Project results can be classified into two categories: those that contribute to food policy definition and those that address food market needs. The former involves the development of innovative approaches and solutions that support policy makers in shaping the future of the food system. The latter involves developing products, processes, and services that meet the evolving demands of the food market.

1. Results enabling Food Policies definition

Project results can enable the development of evidence-based food policies providing valuable information and insights about food related issues to policymakers, which can inform the development of evidence-based food policies. Indeed, data collection and analysis, existing policies

evaluation, best-practices identification and stakeholder engagement are possible results which offer a solid base to food policy definition process.

2. Results addressing Market needs

Project results can help address food market needs by developing new products, improving sustainability practices, ensuring food safety and quality, improving supply chain management, and understanding consumer behavior. By addressing these needs, the FoodCLIC project can contribute to the development of a more sustainable and efficient food system that meets the needs of consumers and industry stakeholders.

TPOLOGY OF RESULTS

Considering these two objectives (Food policies definition and Market need satisfaction), the Key Exploitable Results of the FoodCLIC project have been classified by the Consortium according to several typologies:

- ***guidelines, tools, frameworks:* guidelines and tools are designed to support the implementation of sustainable food chains and promote circularity, while frameworks provide a structured approach for measuring the environmental and economic impact of food chain innovations;**
- ***training materials:* aim to disseminate the project results and provide education on sustainable food chains to a wider audience;**
- ***products:* such as software for optimizing food chain management and innovative packaging solutions to reduce food waste;**
- ***business models:* include different ways in which circular economy principles can be applied in the food sector, such as closed-loop supply chain models and collaborative consumption models;**
- ***network for knowledge-sharing:* serves as a platform for knowledge-sharing and collaboration among stakeholders in the food system.**

Together, these results demonstrate the project's commitment to creating innovative solutions for a more sustainable, resilient, and equitable food system.

The Consortium identified at this phase 5 Key Exploitable Results that are classified following the classification just illustrated. For this preliminary analysis, each result was described according to 6 dimensions:

- **Result description**
- **Challenges addressed**
- **Expected benefits**
- **Expected beneficiaries and stakeholders involved**
- **Possible exploitation path**
- **Technology Readiness Level (TRL)**

Table 4: *Proposed FoodCLIC Key Exploitable Results, classified according to objective and typology*

RESULT	OBJECTIVE	TPOLOGY
CLIC framework for integrated food policies and food-sensitive planning frameworks	Enabling Food Policies definition	Framework
Innovative monitoring and evaluation framework	Enabling Food Policies definition	Framework
Guidelines, tools and recommendations for food policy development	Enabling Food Policies definition	Guidelines, tools
Knowledge Hub – an open access metadata repository of findings, best practices and recommendations	Enabling Food Policies definition and Enabling market need	Product
Innovative and inclusive business models	Enabling market need	Business model

4.1.1 CLIC FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATED FOOD POLICIES AND FOOD-SENSITIVE PLANNING FRAMEWORKS

The CLIC framework is a novel conceptual framework that integrates four key dimensions of social, environmental, spatial, and sectoral "integration" to guide policy, planning, and practice-based interventions in urban food environments. The framework emphasizes the need to consider co-benefits, rural-urban linkages, social inclusion, and connectivities between food and other complex systems. By promoting a holistic and integrated approach to food sustainability, the CLIC framework aims to improve urban food environments and associated city-region food systems, while generating sustainability co-benefits (economic, social and environmental goals).

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

The CLIC framework addresses several challenges facing city-region food systems (including fragmentation of responsibilities across multiple Departments, Ministries, and State agencies), asymmetries of power between food system actors and between levels of governance, and increasing corporate control exercised by agribusiness and transnational companies. Additionally, the framework addresses the need to strengthen rural-urban linkages, enhance social inclusion, and recognize the co-benefits of sustainability strategies that may impact other parts of a system.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

The CLIC framework is expected to generate several benefits, including the development of more integrated urban food policies that realize sustainability co-benefits, create new connectivities and linkages between food and other complex systems, strengthen rural-urban linkages, and enhance social inclusion. The framework also aims to overcome conflicts of interest between entrepreneurs, health professionals, and environmental NGOs through innovative business models. Ultimately, the CLIC framework will contribute to improving urban food environments and associated city-region food systems while generating sustainability co-benefits.

EXPECTED BENEFICIARIES AND STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The expected beneficiaries of the CLIC framework are diverse and include policymakers, urban planners, entrepreneurs, health professionals, environmental NGOs, and communities. The framework is intended to be used by stakeholders from the quadruple helix (representing government, industry, academia, and civil society). The involvement of these stakeholders is crucial to ensure the successful implementation and uptake of the framework.

POSSIBLE EXPLOITATION PATH

The exploitation of the CLIC framework may lead to the development of policy and planning interventions that incorporate the four pillars of integration, the establishment of networks and partnerships to promote the uptake of the framework and the creation of training programs and capacity-building initiatives to support the implementation of the framework. The framework can also be used to develop innovative business models that recognize the co-benefits of sustainability strategies and overcome conflicts of interest between different stakeholders. Considering the model proposed by the Consortium, the exploitation path of the CLIC framework is considered the non-commercial one.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL (TRL)

The CLIC framework can be considered at the beginning of the project as TRL7 “*system prototyping demonstration in operational environment*” (refinement of innovative strategies and (re)testing in a relevant environment with relevant stakeholders). The TRL that is intended to reach at the end of the project is TRL9 “*actual solutions proven through testing and implementation in operational real world*”.

4.1.2 INNOVATIVE MONITORING AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

The FoodCLIC project proposes an innovative Food Sustainability Tool and an integrated Reflexive Monitoring and Dynamic Evaluation framework (RMDE). The Food Sustainability Tool aims to assess the GHG [Greenhouse Gases] emissions of food production and consumption patterns through the indicator of Carbon Footprint (CF) and the main land-cover categories according to the EU COPERNICUS - 2018 Corinne Land Cover (CLC). The RMDE framework supports the assessment of policy-, planning- and practice-based interventions in urban food environments. The RMDE framework combines different methodological approaches, such as participatory action research, systems thinking, and transformational learning, to provide a comprehensive and adaptable tool for evaluating the impact of interventions on the four key dimensions of social, environmental, spatial, and sectoral “integration” of city-region food systems.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

The Sustainability Tool and the RMDE framework address several challenges in the evaluation of urban food environments, including the lack of integration across different dimensions of food

systems, the limited involvement of stakeholders and communities in the evaluation process, and the lack of flexibility to adapt to changing contexts and feedback from stakeholders.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

The Sustainability Tool and the RMDE framework are expected to provide several benefits, including the improvement of policies aiming to develop sustainable food environments, a more comprehensive and integrated understanding of the impact of interventions on city-region food systems, a more participatory and inclusive evaluation process that involves a wide range of stakeholders and communities, and a more adaptable and flexible approach to evaluation that can respond to changing contexts and feedback from stakeholders.

EXPECTED BENEFICIARIES AND STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The Sustainability Tool and the RMDE framework are expected to benefit a wide range of stakeholders and beneficiaries, including policy makers, urban planners, community organizations, civil society groups, and citizens. The framework involves the active participation of these stakeholders and beneficiaries in the evaluation process, ensuring that their feedback and perspectives are taken into account in the assessment of interventions.

POSSIBLE EXPLOITATION PATH

The Sustainability Tool and the RMDE framework can be exploited by incorporating them into urban planning and policy-making processes, through the development of training and capacity-building programs for practitioners and stakeholders, and the dissemination of their findings and recommendations through academic publications, conferences, and workshops. Considering the model proposed by the Consortium, the exploitation path of these tools is considered the non-commercial one.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL (TRL)

The Sustainability Tool and the RMDE framework are both considered at the beginning of the Food CLIC project at a TRL6 “prototyping implementations on full-scale realistic problems”. Considering that further refinement and validation are needed to ensure their applicability in different contexts and their effectiveness in generating transformative change in city-region food systems, the expected TRL at the end of the project is TRL9 “*actual solutions proven through testing and implementation in operational real world*”.

4.1.3. KNOWLEDGE HUB

The Knowledge Hub is a digital platform developed as part of the FoodCLIC project, aimed at facilitating knowledge-sharing and promoting sustainable city-region food systems. The Hub offers a comprehensive set of practical guidelines and tools, including innovative decision-support tools, monitoring frameworks, and impact assessment frameworks. It also provides downloadable self-learning packages for local and regional governments and FPNs to share lessons learned, with guidelines for replication that take into account context-specific needs and priorities.

The contents of the Knowledge Hub will be accessible through conventional search engines and metadata derived from the learning needs of the LLs. It will include various forms of content, such as documents, videos, podcasts, interactive maps, and games, to enhance the user experience. The Hub will also enable the posting of events and blogs and facilitate regular dialogue between stakeholders engaged with city-region food systems.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

One of the main challenges addressed by the Knowledge Hub is the fragmentation of knowledge and information related to city-region food systems. With the vast amount of information available, it can be difficult for stakeholders to access and apply relevant knowledge to their specific contexts. The Hub aims to address this challenge by providing a centralized platform where stakeholders can easily access and share information and experiences related to sustainable city-region food systems.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

The Knowledge Hub is expected to provide several benefits, including:

- Improved access to relevant knowledge and information related to sustainable city-region food systems;
- Enhanced networking and collaboration opportunities between stakeholders across different sectors and geographies;
- Increased visibility and dissemination of best practices and innovative approaches to sustainable city-region food systems;
- Improved capacity for stakeholders to make informed decisions and take action on city-region food system issues.

EXPECTED BENEFICIARIES AND STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The Knowledge Hub is designed to benefit a wide range of stakeholders involved in sustainable city-region food systems, including policymakers, urban planners, researchers, civil society, NGOs and practitioners. These stakeholders can use the Hub to access and share knowledge and experiences, collaborate on initiatives and projects, and participate in discussions related to sustainable city-region food systems.

POSSIBLE EXPLOITATION PATH

The Knowledge Hub can be exploited in several ways to support sustainable city-region food systems. For example, policymakers and urban planners can use the Hub to access and share information related to best practices for city-region food system governance and planning. Researchers can use the Hub to disseminate their findings and connect with other researchers working on similar topics. Civil society organizations and community groups can use the Hub to access information and resources to support their advocacy and community organizing efforts. According to the model proposed by the Consortium, the exploitation path of Knowledge Hub can be both commercial and non-commercial.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL (TRL)

The Knowledge Hub can be considered at the beginning of the project as TRL7 “*system prototyping demonstration in operational environment*” (refinement of innovative strategies and (re)testing in a relevant environment with relevant stakeholders). The Hub is also a dynamic platform that is constantly evolving as new knowledge and experiences are shared by its users, and as new functionalities are developed to meet user needs: the TRL that is intended to reach at the end of the project is TRL9 “*actual solutions proven through testing and implementation in operational real world*”.

4.1.4. INNOVATIVE SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS MODELS

The FoodCLIC project aims to develop innovative and inclusive business models that are sustainable, and based on the synergies between public health, the environment, the economy and social welfare. To achieve this, the project will conduct analyses to identify the social, environmental and economic returns to investment that characterizes these innovations, and advise entrepreneurs on the specific financial, human resources, and infrastructural needs to support their transformation towards more inclusive and sustainable food environments.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

The main challenges addressed by the development of an innovative and inclusive business model include limited access to urban markets for local and regional food producers and processors, and the lack of equitable distribution of healthy food to low-income and marginalized communities.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

The innovative and inclusive business model is expected to bring several benefits, including:

- Increased access to urban markets for local and regional food producers and processors
- Improved distribution of healthy and locally produced food to low-income and marginalized communities
- Creation of new business opportunities and employment in the local food sector
- Promotion of sustainable food systems and reduction of food waste
- Improved food security and health outcomes for urban residents

EXPECTED BENEFICIARIES AND STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The expected beneficiaries include local and regional food producers and processors, particularly those serving low-income and marginalized communities, urban residents, and local and regional governments. Other stakeholders involved in the model include food retailers, distributors, and community-based organizations working on food justice and equity issues, including food banks.

POSSIBLE EXPLOITATION PATH

The exploitation path for the innovative and inclusive business models necessarily includes the analysis of the context in which they will be implemented and the market need – considering that business models developed could also be replicated in other cities and regions with similar challenges and opportunities. The exploitation paths proposed are the commercial and the impact ones.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL (TRL)

Starting from a TRL7, innovative and inclusive business models will be tested under the FoodCLIC project (WP3) and have thus the potential for immediate implementation in other cities and regions, going to a forecasted TRL9.

4.1.5. GUIDELINES, TOOLS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The FoodCLIC project aims to provide guidelines, tools, and recommendations for food policy development. The guidelines will cover various aspects of food policy, including governance, planning, and regulation. The tools will assist policymakers in developing evidence-based policies that promote sustainable and healthy food systems. The recommendations will address the challenges and opportunities of city-region food systems and provide guidance on how to foster cross-sectoral cooperation and community engagement.

CHALLENGES ADDRESSED

The guidelines, tools, and recommendations developed through the FoodCLIC project aim to address several challenges, including the need to promote sustainable and healthy food systems, the need for evidence-based policymaking, the need for cross-sectoral cooperation, and the need for community engagement.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

The guidelines, tools, and recommendations developed through the FoodCLIC project are expected to benefit a wide range of stakeholders, including policy makers, researchers, and civil society organizations. Policy makers will be able to develop evidence-based policies that promote sustainable and healthy food systems, while researchers will be able to use the tools and recommendations to advance knowledge in the field. Civil society organizations will be able to use the guidelines, tools, and recommendations to advocate for more sustainable and equitable food systems.

EXPECTED BENEFICIARIES AND STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The expected beneficiaries of the guidelines, tools, and recommendations developed through the FoodCLIC project include policymakers at the local, regional, and national levels, researchers, civil society organizations, and community members. The stakeholders involved in the development and dissemination of the guidelines, tools, and recommendations include the FoodCLIC project partners, policy makers, civil society organizations, and researchers.

POSSIBLE EXPLOITATION PATH

The guidelines, tools, and recommendations developed through the FoodCLIC project can be exploited in several ways. They can be disseminated through various channels, including online

platforms, conferences, and workshops. An active role will be covered by the eight cities of the FoodCLIC project and by the other project's partners. The project partners can work with policymakers and civil society organizations to ensure that the guidelines, tools, and recommendations are integrated into policy development processes. The guidelines, tools, and recommendations can also be adapted to different contexts and settings, making them useful beyond the scope of the FoodCLIC project.

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL (TRL)

The technology readiness level of the guidelines, tools, and recommendations developed through the Food CLIC project is relatively high. The project relies on existing technologies, such as online platforms and data analysis tools, to develop and disseminate the guidelines, tools, and recommendations. However, the guidelines, tools, and recommendations will require ongoing updates and refinement to ensure that they remain relevant and effective over time.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Exploitation analysis and monitoring of FoodCLIC results will be, as already explained in this Deliverable, a continuous process that will run alongside all WPs activities for the whole project duration – till Month 54. The results proposed and identified by the Consortium within the present Deliverable are preliminary and currently still in their early development phase or even not still ongoing yet, so the Exploitation Plan must be reviewed, further developed and integrated in the following years. Such an iterative and fine-tuning process will be allowed thanks to the continuous feedback and alignments with all project participants and WP Leaders, as well as the LLs that will occur during the project life and that will be fundamental to better understand and deepen the potential of each result. The final Exploitation Plan (M54) will include a detailed description of activities and tools to exploit in the best way each Key Exploitable Result; such action plan will leverage the innovative and participatory approach and the experience as Innovation Hub of the Consortium.

In order to define a proper overview of the impacts provided by FoodCLIC results, a specific analysis will be conducted and integrated into the Exploitation plan in the following months. Moreover, IPR issues will be taken into careful account. At the present stage IPR management is ruled out in FoodCLIC Consortium Agreement, which sets out all needed provisions. Further analysis will be developed and implemented according to the future degree of implementation and foreseen exploitation of each asset, in relation to specific products and/or business models developed by LLs project partners.

According to this approach, in the next months the Consortium will:

- **considering potential additional results to be integrated into the Exploitation Plan not initially foreseen, or removing proposed results;**
- **enlarge and refine the Exploitation Plan through the inclusion of stakeholder target groups, activity plan to exploit each Key Exploitable Result included;**
- **define plans and agreements on assets exploitation, detailing also in-depth IPR management issues.**

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PARTNERS

CONTACT US:

www.foodclik.eu

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